

Antibody Characterization Report for **SLC22A14 (UniProt ID: Q9Y267)** YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Solute carrier family 22 member 14

Short protein name used in this report: SLC22A14

Alternative names: Organic cation transporter-like 4 (ORCTL-4)

Gene name: *SLC22A14* (*OCTL2*, *ORCTL4*)

Uniprot ID: human: Q9Y267, mouse: Q497L9

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science¹. In this study, we characterized six SLC22A14 commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol^{2,3} based on comparing read-outs in knockout (KO) samples and isogenic parental controls (wild-type; WT). We identified a well-performing human reactive antibody and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. Evidence of appropriate SLC22A14 protein expression in testis is shown elsewhere⁴. Testis lysates from parental and *SLC22A14* KO mice were kindly donated by Dr. Keiichiro at Yogo Shizuoka University, Japan⁵. Additionally, *SLC22A14* overexpression cell lines were obtained from the RESOLUTE consortium⁶ and used in this study.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
RESOLUTE	CE0002	-	Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK 293	WT
RESOLUTE	CE05XB-A	-	Nt. HA-tagged-HEK 293 SLC22A14-WTOE-p2*	SLC22A14 overexpression cell line
RESOLUTE	CE0287-Q	-	Ct. HA-tagged HEK 293 SLC22A14-WTOE-p1*	SLC22A14 overexpression cell line

Nt=N terminus; Ct=C terminus

*The pENTRY pDONR221_SLC22A14 plasmid used to insert the *SLC22A14* gene is available at Addgene (plasmid #131999; n2t.net/addgene:131999)

Table 2: Summary of the SLC22A14 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications	Species reactivity (from vendors)
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP43892	QC14072-90513	AB_2048063	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb	H
GeneTex	GTX00905	822105922	AB_3096343	polyclonal	-	rabbit		Wb, IF	M
GeneTex	GTX46827	822105898	AB_11174539	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb	H
Novus Biologicals	NBP1-59398	QC14072-90513	AB_11019060	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb	H
Proteintech	17820-1-AP	82389	AB_2878445	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.75	Wb	H
Sunlong Biotech	SL24072R	AG02105189	n/a	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	IF	M

Wb=western blot, IF=immunofluorescence, n/a=not available, H=human, M=mouse

Materials and methods

Cell culture

Cells (listed in Table 1) were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare, cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent, cat. number 609-065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent, cat. number 450201). Prior to cell lysis, *SLC22A14* overexpression cell lines at 80% confluence were induced with 1 µg/ml of Doxycycline (Cedarlane, cat. number DB0889) for ~18 h.

Antibodies

All the *SLC22A14* antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120).

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure³. HEK 293 WT and *SLC22A14* Nt and Ct overexpression cell lines (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106)

or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Figure 1: SLC22A14 antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

Figure 1: SLC22A14 antibody screening by western blot (2/2)

Figure 1: SLC22A14 antibody screening by western blot.

35 µg of lysates from WT and *SLC22A14* KO mouse testes were run side-by-side with 35 µg of lysates from HEK 293 WT, and Nt and Ct. HA-tagged *SLC22A14* overexpression cell lines. Samples were processed for western blot with the indicated SLC22A14 antibodies. The Ponceau S-stained transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were used at 1/500. The predicted species reactivities, also listed in Table 2, are indicated in between parentheses for each corresponding antibody. Predicted band size: 66.6 kDa. H=human; M=mouse; Nt=N terminus, Ct=C terminus, DOX=doxycycline.

Note: lysates from mouse tissues were not prepared fresh before processing by SDS-PAGE.

References

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